

Nano-engineered Graphene Polymer Composites With Self-health Monitoring

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Outline

- **Bottlenecks** of Today's Structural Health Monitoring (SHM)
- Nano-engineered Sensing – from *Distributed*, through *Quasi-diffuse*, to *Fully-disperse Sensing* (An Initiative to “**Sensor-free**”-inspired SHM)
- Sensor Development, Morphological Analysis, and Sensing Mechanism Interpretation
- Concluding Remarks

Bottlenecks of Today's SHM

Biological sensing-inspired SHM

Sensing network – most fundamental yet most critical

Bottlenecks of Today's SHM

Dense sensor network
(e.g., tomography)

Sparse sensor network
(e.g., Lamb wave-based SHM)

Other Concerns

- Weight/volume penalty
- Use of unwieldy cables and wires
- Degradation of local mechanical strength
- De-attachment between the host structure and sensors due to adhesive degradation

To compromise “**sensing cost**” with “**sensing effectiveness**”

State of the Art of Nanocomposite-based Sensors

- Emerging nanotechnology boosts development of new sensors, in virtue of superior mechanical and electrical properties of nanocomposites.
- Development of **piezoresistive strain sensors** made from various types of nanocarbon.

Limitations:

- Global parameter**, reflecting properties between two electrodes. It can only **qualitatively** locate damage;
- Limited information** on damage details. It only indicates occurrence of damage right **beneath the sensor patch** (damage distant from the patch would not alter measured resistance);
- Responsive to static or at very low-frequency strain of large magnitudes**, under which damage may phenomenally amend the resistor network formed by nanofillers. (reportedly, the highest frequency a nanocomposite sensor can be responsive is **~2 kHz*** or **~10 kHz#**)

$$\Delta R/R_0$$

* Qiu L, et al. Ultrafast dynamic piezoresistive response of graphene-based cellular elastomers. Adv Mater 28, 194-200 (2016).

Liu S, et al. Ultrafast dynamic pressure sensors based on graphene hybrid structure. ACS Appl Mater Interfaces 9, 24148-24154 (2017).

Objectives

- To develop nano-engineered *in-situ* sensing network approach, to strike a **balance between “sensing cost” and “sensing effectiveness”** for SHM applications;
- To be responsive to **ultrasonic** wave signals (**high-frequency + ultralow magnitude**);
- To deploy the developed sensors easily and cost-effectively to form a sensor network, **sprayable** or **coatable** on structural surfaces using **additive manufacturing** such as spraying process, inkjet printing, etc.

VS.

Nanotechnology
in-situ sensing
Printed electronics
3D printing

from **Distributed** to **Diffuse Sensing**

Sensing Mechanism

When elastic disturbance (ultrasonic waves) traversing the nanocomposites

Elastic waves to modulate nano-architecture of nanofillers in the percolating network

Tunnelling effect

$$R = R_{particle} + R_{contact} + R_{tunnel}$$

$$R_{tunnel} = \frac{V}{AJ} = \frac{h^2 d}{Ae^2 \sqrt{2m\lambda}} \exp\left(\frac{4\pi d}{h} \sqrt{2m\lambda}\right)$$

Sensor Development

Nanocarbon from higher to lower aspect ratios varying from **~8000** (long MWCNTs), **~4000** (medium MWCNTs) down to **<10** (CB),

Long multiwall Carbon Nanotubes

Medium multiwall Carbon Nanotubes

2-D Graphene

Carbon Black (CB)

rope-like nanofiller
(e.g. MWCNT)

sphere-like nanofiller
(e.g. CB)

Entanglement and aggregation

Agglomerate in clusters

Sensor Development

2-D nanofiller (e.g. graphene)

0.5wt%

1wt%

2wt%

2D Graphene+CB / PVDF (PVP)

Sensing Mechanism

Hysitron PI 85 pico-indenter

Quanta 450 FEG SEM

Sensor Preparation

Nanocomposites deposited on polyimide substrate via screen printing

Sensor Preparation

Printed
circuits

Sensor Performance

2 kHz-450 kHz

500 kHz-1400 kHz

From *Distributed* to *Quasi-diffuse*

From *Distributed* to *Quasi-diffuse*

From *Distributed* to *Quasi-diffuse*

From *Quasi-diffuse* to *Fully-disperse*

● PZT actuators
 Printed electrical circuits and electrodes
 Graphene nanoparticles

“Sensor-free”-inspired SHM

Concluding Remarks

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Thank You

